

DEVELOPMENT OF OBTAINING A DRY EXTRACT FROM THE HERB OF EQUISETUM ARVENSE

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Relevance: the importance of marketing research on the diuretic pharmaceutical market is determined by their key role in modern therapeutic practice. This group of drugs is widely used in the treatment of such common conditions as arterial hypertension, chronic heart failure, edema of various etiologies, and nephrological pathologies. One such plant, widely used in folk medicine, is horsetail (*Equisetum arvense*). Horsetail infusions have a comprehensive effect on the body. They stimulate the elimination of excess fluid, which helps manage swelling, and combat inflammation in the urinary tract. Horsetail also has general tonic, hemostatic, healing, and astringent properties. It is effective for cystitis, urethritis, and swelling caused by kidney dysfunction or heart failure.

Purpose of the study: development of a rational method for obtaining a dry extract from horsetail herb.

Materials and methods: four methods were studied to obtain an alcoholic extract from horsetail: maceration, fractional maceration, percolation, and repercolation. All of these methods are standard in the industrial production of alcoholic extracts from plant materials. At the end of each extraction step or the entire process, the resulting liquids were combined by gravity. The remaining pulp was pressed, and the resulting extract was added to the corresponding extracts. The combined extracts were then settled at a temperature below 10°C for two days and filtered.

For the experiment, dried plant material was ground to the desired fraction. The resulting powder was dried in a rotary evaporator at 40-50°C. The study was conducted using standard methods, beginning with determining the optimal process parameters for medicinal plant material and culminating in establishing quality standards for the final product. The technological characteristics of medicinal plant material include such parameters as the degree of grinding, particle size distribution (fractional composition), bulk density (bulk density), solvent absorption capacity (extractant absorption coefficient), and ease of movement (flowability). Also important are the time required to extract the active substances (extraction duration) and the number of interactions between the material and solvent (multiplicity). To determine the optimal degree of grinding, a quantitative analysis of the total tannins in the experimentally obtained extracts was conducted. The quality of the extracts was assessed based on the dry residue. Based on these data, the repercolation method was chosen as the most effective.

Results: the extraction yielded a dark-brown liquid product with a greenish tint and a distinct odor. This liquid extract was then concentrated by vacuum evaporation on a rotary evaporator. The final step involved vacuum drying to obtain a dry extract, a hygroscopic brown powder with a residual moisture content of no more than 5% and a characteristic aroma.

Conclusions: based on the dry residue content, the most optimal extraction method was chosen – repercolation, and the most optimal extractant was 40% ethyl alcohol.